

PROBLEMATIC AND MODULAR TECHNOLOGY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of designing pedagogical technologies in the educational system is scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

Key words: Education system, science, technology, interest in learning, globalization era, national interests of each nation, each independent state, own culture, ancient values, native language, scientific and pedagogical experience, etc.

Problem-based education is a form of education that emerged as a positive result of research and experiments conducted in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. When we think about problem-based education, what is this education? What are its theoretical foundations? How does it differ from traditional education? What is the purpose of problem-based learning? We are faced with the question of how a teacher implements problem-based education.

Problem-based education is the teacher's activity aimed at effectively solving the problem of which part of the knowledge to be given to the student and in what way. Problem-based education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students at the same time in the lesson, which develops the important character-creative thinking ability of the student. As N. G. Dayri said, the main goal of problem-based education is to bring the student's activity to the same level as the teacher's activity in mastering the complex part of the content studied in the lesson. Problem-based education is influencing students to think freely, express their opinions freely, and further develop their thoughts. In doing so, the student should be able to listen carefully, think independently and alone, think as a team, analyze, discuss as a majority, and express the collected opinion.

If the teacher makes an effective presentation of a new topic, makes good use of exhibitions, and works with some students at the end of the presentation, it can be considered that the learning process has been effective or active. But this method of education is traditional education. Problem-based education requires the teacher to make specific efforts, to take into account every minute of the lesson, to use all his abilities and skills to achieve the desired effect at this time. An important condition for solving this problem is the preparation of the teacher for the upcoming training session. In the preparation process, it is necessary to take into account all aspects of problem-based education and

develop its method. Teachers face a number of difficulties in preparing for problem-based education. In overcoming these difficulties, the teacher's innovative creative laboratory is of great importance.

One of such difficulties is in choosing a problem-based organization of the lesson and a method of studying the problem. Because the chosen method not only ensures mastery of the learning material, but also it is necessary to ensure independence in students' activities. The second difficulty arises when determining the appearance of problem-based education, that is, does the teacher involve all the students in the class in solving the problem, or does he perform the task to some group of students? This difficulty comes from the teacher's lack of imagination about the problem situation and the description of the problem.

The third trick is to arouse students' interest in the lesson and continuously develop it. Because the experience and skill of the teacher may not be able to regularly focus students' attention on one point.

Based on the collected data on problem-based education, it should be noted that this type of education has 3 aspects from a scientific and methodological point of view.

1. Creating a problematic situation.
2. Setting the problem.
3. Finding a solution to the problem.

A problem situation can be formed in all educational activities. It depends on the teacher how much to paralyze it during the lesson. The importance of the problematic situation is that it focuses students' attention on one place (problem) and teaches students to search and think. When creating a problem situation, it is appropriate for the teacher to tell the students what to focus their attention on.

For example, on the subject of "The Conquest of the Khanate of Khiva by Imperial Russia", it is necessary to draw the attention of readers to two problems. For this, the teacher:

1. How would the subjugation of the Khiva Khanate benefit Russia? creates a problem situation by asking the question and listens to the students' opinions. After hearing all the opinions, he should announce the final conclusion to the question.

2. Analyze the eyes of the Turkmens. Why was the spectacle lightened? With this question, the teacher created a second problematic situation. Pupils act

together with the teacher in the process of solving, express their thoughts and opinions on the problem, and contribute to the solution of the problem.

In the process of solving the problem, the teacher does not tell the students the most necessary idea, but he needs to cite evidence and facts that form this idea.

The problematic situation on the topic "Democracy in Athens":

- Why are Dracon laws called "laws written with mine"?

-What is the difference between today's democracy and the ancient Athens democracy? with such questions you can create a situation.

The situation in the topic "Legislative activity of the Supreme Majlis":

- who participates in the development of the law?

- Which of the laws adopted by the Supreme Council do we know? can be created with questions like

When the teacher sees a problem, he should give instructions and directions to the students to solve the problem and announce the criteria for evaluating their work. The level of complexity of the problem is determined by the knowledge of the students.

The design of a module system of education is of particular importance in the practice of generalized pedagogical technologies of the teaching process. Scientists from far and near foreign countries have proven that this is related to the complete assimilation of educational information by students, and as they move from module to module, their knowledge, skills, and abilities develop.

As a social phenomenon, a person interacts with the reality that surrounds him, strives to learn their essence and understand it through experiments. These experiences are called knowledge as a didactic category. Depending on the volume, quality and type of experiences accumulated by a specific person, his educational and social power and image are evaluated. The deeper and wider his knowledge, the more perfect his outlook. As a result, the acquired knowledge is absorbed into the soul by perfecting the worldview and makes the way of life colorful.

This is especially important in the context of our country's spiritual and educational renewal, transition to socially oriented market relations, and joining the world. In addition, according to some calculations, the development of science in the world accelerated sharply in the second half of the 20th century. During the last 15-20 years, scientific activity has increased twice, and its total value is 3/4 of the total information collected during the history of human society.

In such conditions, that is, in the conditions of the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, it is difficult to bring up the students (students) in accordance with the requirements of the age without updating and changing the form and method of providing information.

The information of the scientific pedagogical theory can be achieved by designing a module system of teaching. Because "Modular education" is related to the word module, it means a closely connected and logically sequenced and complete unit of a given field. It is also an activity aimed at learning the fundamental laws of life. Another important feature of modular training is "... the best adaptation of the human brain to the learning system. According to researchers N. Avliyokulov, A. Zhukovskiy, G. Kalinichenko, M. Mironova, G. Razorenova, J. Baisalov, M. Choshanov, and others, modular teaching is based on the modular organization of the tissues of the human brain.

"Human brain tissue - writes N.H. Avliyokulov, about 15 billion. consisting of neurons (nerve cells) or hardware modules. Tissue cells are in numerous collisions with each other. The number of collisions of one cell and its tumor with another cell and its tumor reaches 6 thousand. Therefore, the number of contacts in the brain tissue is astronomical (150 00000000x6000). From this point of view, the module is considered as a cell of the educational process. At the same time, this cell is composed of elements that have a unique integrity and structure in the informational community.

Thus, modular educational technology involves learning a certain subject by dividing it into large groups or parts. In this case, it should not be overlooked that educational information is close to each other in terms of content, is logically correct, and is compatible.

So, why are we talking about modular teaching in the educational process today? What necessity demands this? It is known that in the 9th session of the first convocation of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic, the "National Program of Personnel Training" was adopted, and their main goal was "to fundamentally reform the field of education, to rid it of ideological views and prejudices left over from the past, is to create a national system of highly qualified personnel training that meets high moral and ethical requirements at the level of developed democratic countries"

This need, first of all, determines the need to radically update the educational system, educational content, methods, forms and tools of education and create a modular system of education.

Secondly, as we noted above, the acceleration of scientific progress led to the acceleration and renewal of the growth of technology and its working technology. This, in turn, requires acceleration and automation of human mental work. This can be achieved only by training talented young people, highly educated specialists who can find their place in the information revolution and contribute to its development.

Thirdly, in the conditions of the development of science, technology and its working technology, primary school students are required to individualize their studies, to start independent, creative activities. It is felt that the task now is to use educational technology capable of meeting these requirements, that is, teaching students to work creatively with scientific and technical information, to think non-standard.

Fourth, computerization, automation of all aspects of the national economy (agriculture, industry, construction, medicine, education, etc.), wide application of scientific achievements to the development of a place in the module of the national personnel training program, specialists is that he set the task of a new approach to training.

Fifth, in the continuous system of primary education, to accelerate training in order to prepare individuals who can respond to the demands of time, science, and technology development and to develop it, to make maximum use of the talents, opportunities, and conditions of each person. Also, in order to provide the teaching process with complete information, to design education, to guarantee the result, to establish computer training, distance training to clarify the goal, and finally;

Sixth, each person as a biosociety has individual-spiritual characteristics, abilities and needs. Accordingly, the development of these features of today's education should be able to focus on solving educational tasks.

Seventhly, it is the fact that the learning goals, attitudes, and attention of primary school students are increasing, but the expansion of mental capabilities is always neglected in the training of specialists, which leads to a decrease in the motivation to study. However, an important component of modern pedagogical technology, which is able to meet the above needs and adapt more to the demands of science and time in the secondary special, vocational and higher education system focused on the training of specialist personnel, is the modular teaching technology. In addition, the record of "... new pedagogical and information technologies, acceleration of student training using the modular system of training" for the organization and development of the two-level

system of higher education of the National Program of Personnel Training is a proof of the relevance of modular education technology.

As we noted in the previous paragraph, in the process of rapid development of science, technology, and its working technology, it is necessary to accelerate teaching in front of independence education, to differentiate and individualize education, to develop independent and creative thinking of learners. It is an urgent problem to apply modular educational technology capable of satisfying students such as development, formation of skills to find their place in the rapidly changing conditions of information flow, development of critical thinking, talent, abilities, etc. is standing.

The essence of the modular teaching technology is that it is adapted to the learning system of the human brain and relies on the modular organization of brain tissue. That is why it means a closely and logically connected unity of a certain field of science and is an activity aimed at creating an opportunity to master this field perfectly. After all, "Modular is a unit of educational material, designed on the basis of certain principles, aimed at learning the fundamental concepts of science."

That's why modular training implies gradual assimilation of educational information.

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